

Pharmacists' knowledge on the possible medication and vaccine for COVID-19

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Abstract

Pharmacists are the medication experts of the healthcare field; they play a role in the therapeutic regimen of patients. It is part of their job to know what medications are used for certain sicknesses, how they are administered, and relevant information about medications that they should give out and explain to the patients. The Coronavirus Disease 2019 also known as COVID-19 took the world by surprise and placed a heavy strain on the healthcare systems of countries it affected. It did not have any available medication for its treatment or any vaccine for its prevention, but as time progressed several pharmaceutical companies researched, did clinical trials and came up with several compounds that can be used to treat the disease. This study aimed to assess the knowledge of pharmacists on the available medication and vaccine for the treatment and prevention of COVID-19. This study made use of a survey questionnaire which focused on COVID-19 available medications and vaccines. So far, there has only been one approved medication for COVID-19 and one authorized vaccine. The results of the survey showed that pharmacists have adequate and emerging knowledge about this topic. Given that new information keeps coming, this result is acceptable and understandable as it also shows that pharmacists are also striving to learn and keep up with the new trends and updates about treatment options for COVID-19.

Keywords: Pharmacists; COVID-19; Medication; Vaccine.

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Introduction

Pharmacists are medical experts who are very important in helping patients get the best possible results from their treatment plan. Pharmacists are considered as a trusted source of knowledge and advice. Whenever a patient walks into a pharmacy, a pharmacist ensures that the patient does not leave without being provided with the proper and accurate information that the patient needs to know. Pharmacists are the ones responsible for receiving and interpreting prescriptions, dispensing medications and compounding them when needed, ensuring that the patients are given the correct doses at the right time, and provide patient counselling to ensure patients have the proper information regarding their medications. The American Pharmacists Association has determined that pharmacists have eight essential medication related responsibilities. The eight responsibilities are ensuring access to medication, supplying medication information, evaluating the medication appropriateness for each patient, help in improving medication adherence of patients, providing health and wellness services, medication management, assessing health status, and coordinating care transitions (Dopp et al., 2020).

COVID-19 shocked the whole world and have really caused a lot of demand and stress on the healthcare field. This virus has infected a lot of people and has claimed lives as well. It started without any cure known for it, no vaccines available as a precaution for it. Last October 22, 2020, the U.S Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has approved one antiviral drug for the treatment of COVID-19 (US FDA,

2020). Every other treatment is based on symptoms of the patient. There has been one vaccine so far that has been authorized for use in the prevention of the disease. Pharmacists should stay up to date of the current trends in the treatment of COVID-19 as they are the medication experts that people should be able to rely on.

The coronavirus disease, also called COVID-19, started in Wuhan, China. It is a highly contagious viral infection caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2, or SARS-CoV-2 (Dousari et al., 2020). The genetic analysis of the virus has determined that there is a phylogenetic relation between SARS-CoV-2 and the SARS-like bat viruses. Scientists believe that bats might be the original source of the virus, but it is not clear how the virus first spread to humans. The rapid transmission from one human to another has however been confirmed (Shereen et al., 2020).

When the outbreak happened, there was no available medicine that could treat or prevent the virus from spreading. Clinical management of COVID-19 involves procedures to stop the spread of the virus and provide care to patients. This includes giving extra oxygen and using a machine to help breathing when needed. There have been different guidelines and emergency medicines that have been approved for the therapeutic management of COVID-19, however, some of them have shown to have no effect on treatment and on reducing mortality of patients infected with the disease (Fagni et al., 2021).

The US Food and Drug Administration gave permission to use chloroquine phosphate and hydroxychloroquine sulfate under an emergency use authorization (EUA). This allowed these medicines to be added to the strategic national stockpile (SNS) (Bull-Otterson et al., 2020). Some studies found that these drugs had a small positive effect on people who were infected with COVID-19. However, some studies, even though they showed some positive results, do not recommend the use of it for COVID-19 patients (Mahévas et al., 2020). After a few months, the US FDA released a statement revoking the emergency use authorization (EUA) that was issued for hydroxychloroquine sulfate and chloroquine phosphate. Based on factors such as it no longer meets the criteria for issuing an EUA for it and the emerging scientific data. Due to the series of serious cardiac adverse events that has been happening to patients who are given the drug. The known adverse risks already surpass the known potential benefits. Therefore, the US FDA has cautioned against the use of the said medicines outside the hospital setting and clinical trials due to the risks of developing heart problems (US FDA, 2020).

Due to the disease not having medications that can treat or prevent the spread of it, supportive care is utilized especially for those who are severe and critical and require hospital admission. Patients with serious or critical illness require full treatment. This may include oxygen and breathing support for low blood oxygen levels, as well as treating complications like infections and managing other health issues the patient may have, such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), heart failure, and asthma.

Patients that are too frail or have multiple co-morbidities or have a very high risk of death are considered not suitable for escalation to intensive care. However, there is still moral obligation to provide them with good symptomatic treatment to avoid the suffering of the patient. Patients who have COVID-19 in order to have comprehensive care must be screened thoroughly to know the approach to management (Bajwah et al., 2020).

Another approach that they went into for the treatment of COVID-19 is convalescent plasma. Convalescent plasma is blood from people who have recovered from COVID-19. It is given to infected patients through a blood transfusion. Studies show that convalescent plasma can significantly lower the risk of death within 28 days, which is most effective for people in the early stages of the disease (Salazar et al., 2020).

In the Philippines, COVID-19 patients are treated with symptomatic management and supportive care. The Philippines health care system has somehow suffered from the effects of this pandemic being that hospital and laboratory facilities were ill-prepared for the spread of the disease. Patients who are infected are given medications such as antivirals like oseltamivir which may be given with support systems such as ventilation or oxygen support depending on the severity of the patient (Edrada et al., 2020).

Recently, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration has approved one medication that can be used as treatment for COVID-19. The antiviral drug Veklury (Remdesivir) has been approved for use in adults and children aged 12 and older who weigh at least 40 kilograms. It can only be given in a hospital or healthcare setting that can provide the same level of care as an inpatient hospital (Levien & Baker, 2021). Several clinical trials have shown that the patients that were administered with remdesivir had shortened time of recovery, the recovery time for the placebo group was 15 days but for those that were administered with remdesivir the patients recovered within 10 days which suggests an overall decrease in mortality for COVID-19 patients (Beigel et al., 2020).

In terms of the COVID-19 vaccine, there has not been any approved. However, there are different vaccine candidates that are already undergoing clinical trials. Most of the vaccines being developed use the S antigen, which is a key part of the virus. These vaccines come in different forms, including inactivated, subunit, viral vector, and DNA or mRNA-based vaccines. This is because the S protein is the main target for vaccine development. The Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI) has provided funding to develop vaccines for COVID-19, the companies that participated includes Curevac Inc. (mRNA), Inovio Pharmaceuticals Inc. (DNA), Moderna Inc. (mRNA), University of Queensland (molecular clamp), Novavax (nanoparticles), University of Oxford (adenovirus vector), University of Hong Kong (live-attenuated influenza virus), and Institute of Pasteur (measles vector) (Wu, 2020).

The pharmacy profession has experienced a shift of focus in the past decades, from technical, product-oriented functions to patient-oriented health outcomes by offering counselling information and professional services. This is now known as pharmaceutical care where pharmacists will work hand in hand with other members of the healthcare team and undertake the responsibility of ensuring positive outcomes with respect to the patient's drug therapy (Kokane & Avhad, 2016). During this pandemic, community pharmacists have helped in providing direct patient care and perform frontline duties for their community by delivering medications to patients, educating patients on telehealth services, assessing patients for renewal of chronic medications, performing consultations on minor ailments, clarifying misconceptions about COVID-19 treatments, and contributing to COVID-19 screening. Hospital pharmacists' roles include the management of drug shortages, development of treatment protocols, participation of patients rounds, participant recruitment for clinical trials, exploration of new drugs, medication management advice, and antimicrobial stewardship (Elbeddini et al., 2020). Through this, it is essential for them to stay informed and current about the latest developments in treating illnesses and new vaccines for COVID-19.

Research Objectives

This study aims to:

1. Determine the level of knowledge of the respondents regarding medication treatment for COVID-19.
2. Determine the level of knowledge of the respondents regarding upcoming vaccines for COVID-19.
3. Determine if there is a significant difference between the level of knowledge of the respondents based on their demographics.
4. Determine if there is a significant difference between the level of knowledge of community pharmacists and hospital pharmacists regarding the medication treatment for COVID-19.
5. Determine if there is a significant difference between the level of knowledge of community pharmacists and hospital pharmacists regarding the upcoming vaccines for COVID-19.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the Covid-19 knowledge on medication and vaccination of selected Pharmacists. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the level of knowledge of the respondents about Covid-19 medication and vaccine?
2. Is there a significant difference in the mean score on knowledge about Covid-19 medication and vaccine when they were grouped according to demographic profile?

Scope and Limitations

This research paper only dealt with assessing the knowledge of pharmacists when it comes to medication treatments and authorized vaccines for the fight against COVID-19. The researchers had 50 respondents participate in the study which came from both community and hospital pharmacy. This did not include any other health care team members and did not deal with other aspects of COVID-19. This research paper only dealt with the first approved medication for COVID-19, which was Remdesivir and the first authorized vaccine, which was from Pfizer-BioNTech, other medications, and vaccines was not dealt with.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive type of research and a quantitative approach. This describes data and characteristics about the population or phenomenon being studied. It is used in many fields of research due to its applicability to solve different kinds of problems. It involves description, recording, analysis and interpretation. The research design used by the researcher in this thesis is a descriptive research design.

Sample

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of respondents. The demographic profile of the 50 respondents shows that 24% (12) are male and 76% (38) are female. In terms of pharmacy field, 64% (32) are community pharmacists, while 36% (18) are hospital pharmacists. Regarding years in the profession, 14% (7) have more than three years of experience, whereas 86% (43) have three years or less. For job positions, the majority are staff pharmacists at 66% (33), followed by head pharmacists at 18% (9), clinical pharmacists at 6% (3), senior pharmacists at 4% (2), and both chief and public health pharmacists at 2% (1) each. Among hospital pharmacists, 2% (1) work in government hospitals and 34% (17) in private hospitals. As for sources of information, 10% (5) rely solely on journal articles, 2% (1) use journal articles, scientific articles, and expert columns, 30% (15) use journal articles and social media, 28% (14) use journal articles, social media, and word of mouth, and 2% (1) use journal articles, social media, word of mouth, and books. Additionally, 2% (1) use journal articles and word of mouth, 2% (1) use Lexicomp, 2% (1) use social media, word of mouth, and YouTube videos citing journal sources, 2% (1) rely on word of mouth only, 2% (1) use word of mouth and Monthly Index of Medical Specialties (MIMS), 8% (4) use only social media, and 6% (3) use both social media and word of mouth.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents (n=50)

Profile	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	12	24
	Female	38	76
Type of Pharmacy Field	Community Pharmacist	32	64
	Hospital Pharmacist	18	36
Years in the Profession as Pharmacist	More than 3 years	7	14
	3 years and below	43	86
Job Position/Title	Chief Pharmacist	1	2
	Clinical Pharmacist	3	6
	Staff Pharmacist	33	66
	Head Pharmacist	9	18
	Pharmacist I	1	2
	Public Health Pharmacist	1	2
Type of Hospital Worked for Hospital Pharmacist	Senior Pharmacist	2	4
	Government	1	2
	Private	17	34
Source of Information	Not Applicable	32	64
	Journal Articles Only	5	10
	Journal articles, Scientific articles, Expert advice columns	1	2
	Journal articles and Social media	15	30
	Journal articles, Social media, and Word of mouth	14	28
	Journal articles, Social media, Word of mouth, and books	1	2
	Journal articles and Word of mouth	1	2
	Lexicomp	1	2
	Social media	4	8
	Social media and Word of mouth	3	6
	Social media, Word of mouth, YouTube videos who gather reliable information from primary sources (i.e., Journals)	1	2
	Word of mouth only	1	2
	Word of mouth and MIMS	1	2
	No response	2	4

Sampling Procedures

This study utilized purposive and convenience samplings. Purposive sampling means that in order to be qualified as respondents in this study, respondents should be licensed pharmacists. Convenience sampling means respondents' participation is based on their willingness and availability to participate in the study.

Instruments

This study utilized a self-made assessment that will measure the respondent's knowledge on COVID-19 vaccination and medication. With the assistance of subject matter experts and statistician, the researchers initially developed a 50-item multiple-choice test and were given to pharmacy students to get data needed for item difficulty and discrimination. Out of the 50 items, only 34 items obtained a difficulty index between 0.30-0.70, which has moderate difficulty in the item and considered very good items.

Data Analysis

The following statistics were used to conduct data analysis

Frequency. This was used to get the number of respondents classified based on the sub-level of each demographic profile.

Mean. This is to get the mean scores of Covid-19 knowledge on vaccination and medication.

Percentage. This refers to the proportion or representation of a specific sub-level of a demographic profile.

T-Test for Independent Samples. This is to get the significant difference between 2 groups.

Table 2. Reference Scale for Covid-19 Knowledge on Medication and Vaccination

Range	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
31.50-34.00	Excellent	Exemplary Knowledge
28.50-31.49	Very Good	Proficient Knowledge
25.50-28.49	Good	Developing Knowledge
22.50-25.49	Fair	Emerging Knowledge
21.50-22.49	Need Improvement	Knowledge Needs to Be Improved
Below 21.50	Failed	Unsatisfactory Knowledge

Results and Discussion

Table 3. Level of Knowledge About Medications and Vaccines for COVID-19

Items	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Generic name of approved medication	Correct	40	80%
	Incorrect	10	20%
Brand name of approved medication	Correct	34	68%
	Incorrect	16	33%
Route of administration	Correct	35	70%
	Incorrect	15	30%
Dosage strength	Correct	33	66%
	Incorrect	17	34%
Adverse reaction	Correct	38	76%
	Incorrect	12	24%
Name and type of approved vaccine	Correct	25	50%
	Incorrect	25	50%
No. of dose/shots	Correct	45	90%
	Incorrect	5	10%
Pharmaceutical company of approved vaccine	Correct	16	32%
	Incorrect	34	68%
Required storage of approved vaccine	Correct	27	54%
	Incorrect	23	46%

Table 3 reveals the knowledge of the respondents about certain information regarding the medicine and vaccine that is available in the market for COVID-19. The first variable that was measured for the level of knowledge of the respondents was their knowledge about the generic name of the approved medicine for COVID-19. The approved medication's generic name is Remdesivir, out of the 50 respondents 40 (80%) of them got the correct answer. The US Food and Drug Administration approved the antiviral drug Remdesivir. It will include both adult and pediatric patients who are 12 years old or older and weigh at least 40 kilograms. This is approved for treating COVID-19 that needs hospitalization, and it can only

be given in a hospital or healthcare facility. This is the first medication that is approved by the US FDA for the treatment of COVID-19 (Ross & Rodriguez, 2022).

It is very comforting to know that pharmacists know this information as it is one of the relevant pieces of information about the medicines for COVID. Having majority of the respondents know the correct information can mean that these pharmacists take time to read and learn about the progress of the medications for this disease. The generic name is one of the first pieces of information that is released about medication so it is expected that this should be known especially by pharmacists. One of the most accessible healthcare providers are the pharmacists, therefore it is very vital for them to understand COVID-19's epidemiology, how it is transmitted and how to prevent its spreading. They should also be always up to date and familiar with the latest COVID-19 treatment and prevention guidelines, especially the basic and relevant information such as generic name, brand name, dose, and route of administration (Al-Quteimat & Amer, 2021).

The second variable that was measured for the level of knowledge of the respondents was about their knowledge of the brand name for the approved medicine. The results came back with 34 (68%) of the respondents having the correct response. Although a bit lower from the first variable, it still shows that majority of the respondents have and know the correct information. The brand name for the approved medication of COVID-19 is Veklury. There was one company who did clinical trials for the use of Remdesivir for the treatment of COVID-19. Gilead Sciences, Inc. is the pharmaceutical company that produced and manufactured the antiviral drug Veklury (Remdesivir), the first drug that was approved by the US FDA for the treatment of COVID-19 (Lamb, 2020).

Some of the respondents who had the wrong answer just had the wrong spelling of the brand name, but it can be said that they know or have an idea of the correct answer, just not the accurate one. A study that was done to assess the preference of pharmacists between branded and generic medications, showed that majority of pharmacists preferred generic medications over branded medications. This also carries on to when dispensing, they would suggest generic equivalents instead of the branded ones (Patel et al., 2016).

The third variable is about the respondents' knowledge about the route of administration of the medicine for COVID-19. Survey results showed that 35 (70%) respondents answered this question correctly. The route of administration of Remdesivir is IV infusion. Remdesivir must be prepared and administered only under the supervision of a healthcare provider and must only be administered via intravenous fusion and no other route (Veronin et al., 2021). This can come in handy when patients come and ask for information about the medication. Here in the Philippines, people tend to self-medicate and get medicines from sources that are somehow not trustworthy, pharmacists being able to provide them with the right information, it would lower the risk of people getting the incorrect medicine posing as Remdesivir.

The next variable is about the respondents' knowledge about the dosage strength of the medication for COVID-19. The results of the survey showed that 33 (65%) of the respondents had the right response and information. The dosage strength for Remdesivir is 200 mg for the first dose then 100 mg for the subsequent doses. For adult patients and pediatric patients who are 12 years and older, the recommended dosage is 200 mg for the loading dose and then 100 mg for the maintenance dose for the rest of the regimen (Ross & Rodriguez, 2022). This is relevant information that should be known by the pharmacists especially those in the hospital field as they are the ones that dispense this medication to the patients. If pharmacists do not have the correct information about this factor, it could cause consequences that can either be minor or major.

The fifth variable that was measured was the respondents' level of knowledge about the possible adverse effects of the COVID-19 medication. Majority of the respondents, with 38 (75%) of them having the correct response. One of the adverse effects that can be caused by the COVID-19 medication is anaphylactic shock. Infusion-related hypersensitivity reactions and anaphylactic reactions have been observed during and following the administration of Veklury. Some of the signs and symptoms that were

observed were tachycardia, hypotension, bradycardia, hypertension, hypoxia, dyspnea, rash, nausea, and shivering (Ross & Koss, 2021).

One of the roles of a pharmacist is to provide counselling to patients especially about the medications they are taking. Part of the counselling includes giving out all pertinent information about medications, which includes how to take them, when to take them and its possible side/adverse effects. Patients, especially during this uncertain time would certainly have a lot of questions about the medications that are given/administered to them, pharmacists having the correct information and being able to explain it to patients would really help in reassuring them.

The sixth variable that was measured was the respondents' level of knowledge of the name and the type of the approved vaccine for COVID-19. The results came back with 25 (50%), which is half of the number of respondents, which had the right answer. The name and type of the approved vaccine for emergency use for COVID-19 is mRNA vaccine (BNT162b2). The US Food and Drug Administration issued the first emergency use authorization for a COVID-19 vaccine on December 11, 2020. The vaccine was authorized initially to be administered only to individuals who are 16 years of age and older; however, this approval has been updated on May 10, 2021, the US FDA has now given authorization for this vaccine to be administered to individuals who are adolescents that are 12 to 15 years of age (Wallace et al., 2021).

Immunization is currently not part of the roles of pharmacists here in the Philippines, which might explain why respondents did not much know about the name and type of vaccine approved for COVID-19. However, there have been efforts recently to make immunization as part of the role of our pharmacists. With this in mind, it would be best that pharmacists would know even the most basic information about the vaccine for COVID-19.

The seventh variable that was measured was the respondents' knowledge of the number of dose/shots that is required for the vaccine. The results of the survey showed that 45 (88%) of the respondents had the correct answer. The required number of dose/shot for the COVID-19 vaccine is 2. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention released information about the dosing requirements for the vaccine. This vaccine is meant to be given in a 2-dose series that is separated by 21 days (Kriss et al., 2021). As part of patient counselling, a pharmacist should have this information known and at hand disseminate it to the patients. With a lot of doubts and controversies associated with vaccines, a way of reassuring the patients is to show them that we know the necessary information about what we are giving them and that if they do have questions about it, we would be able to answer them and give them clarification.

The eighth variable that was measured the knowledge of the respondents about the name of the pharmaceutical company that produced the approved vaccine. The results came back with only 16 (31%) having the right answer. Majority, which was at 34 (69%) of the respondents did not know the name of the pharmaceutical company that was able to produce the first vaccine that was approved for use in the possible prevention of COVID-19. Pfizer is the pharmaceutical company that produces and manufactures the first vaccine that was approved for use against COVID-19. People nowadays are quite hesitant to get vaccinated because they feel that the vaccines are rushed and has not undergone the proper and correct processes, but what somehow gets them to trust is the name of the company that produces it. There are some brands that people have come to trust, and mostly they are companies that have been in the industry for long and Pfizer is one of the most trusted pharmaceutical companies not only in the Philippines but all over the world.

The ninth and final variable that was measured in this research about the respondents' level of knowledge is their knowledge about the storage conditions needed for the vaccine. The survey results showed that 27 (53%) of the respondents knew the correct answer. The mRNA-1273 vaccine requires a storage temperature of -70 degrees Celsius (Gao et al., 2021). Vaccines are stored in bio-refrigerators in pharmacies, and it is of importance that they are kept according to required storage conditions to maintain them being viable and prevent them from deteriorating. It is part of the role of pharmacists in regulating the bio-refrigerators and ensure that the vaccines are stored in the right position and at the right temperature.

Table 4. Mean Score on Knowledge About COVID-19 Medication and Vaccine

Demographic Profile	Variables	Mean Score	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	23.25	Fair	Emerging Knowledge
	Female	22.34	Need Improvement	Knowledge needs to be improved
Type of Pharmacy Field	Community Pharmacist	22.53	Fair	Emerging Knowledge
	Hospital Pharmacist	22.61	Fair	Emerging Knowledge
Years in the Profession as Pharmacist	More than 3 years	25.00	Fair	Emerging Knowledge
	3 years and below	22.16	Need Improvement	Knowledge needs to be improved
Total		22.56	Fair	Emerging Knowledge

Table 4 indicates the mean score on knowledge about COVID-19 medication and vaccine. In terms of sex demographic profile, male respondents had a mean score of 23.25, with a verbal description of “Fair” and a verbal interpretation of “Emerging Knowledge,” while female respondents had a mean score of 22.34, described as “Needs Improvement” and interpreted as “Knowledge needs to be improved.” For the type of pharmacy field, community pharmacists had a mean score of 23.53, described as “Fair” and interpreted as “Emerging Knowledge,” while hospital pharmacists had a slightly lower mean score of 22.56, also described as “Fair” with the same interpretation. Regarding years in the profession, pharmacists with more than three years of experience had a mean score of 25.00, with a verbal description of “Fair” and interpretation of “Emerging Knowledge.” In contrast, those with three years or less had a mean score of 22.16, described as “Needs Improvement” and interpreted as “Knowledge needs to be improved.”

In a study done to assess the knowledge and preparedness of hospital pharmacists in Lebanon, the results have shown that pharmacists have about 90% knowledge about the common and basic information about COVID-19. They are aware of what COVID-19 is, how it is transmitted, what steps to take to prevent contracting the disease, and what were the available options for the management of the disease. They get their information from World Health Organization (WHO) and CDC and try as much as possible to read materials related to COVID-19 and updates every day (Zeenny et al., 2020).

In another study, it has shown that community pharmacists have adequate knowledge of what COVID-19 is, what virus causes it, how it is transmitted, the signs and symptoms that an infected patient exhibits, and different ways of non- pharmacological intervention for prevention of the disease, and what medications can be used to manage symptoms and provide supportive care to infective patients (Shrestha et al., 2020).

Table 5. Test for Significant Difference

Demographic Profile	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
Sex	0.648	Not Significant	Accept
Type of Pharmacy Field	0.968	Not Significant	Accept
Years in the Profession as Pharmacist	0.331	Not Significant	Accept

*Significant at .05 alpha level

Based on the analysis of demographic profiles, such as sex (p=0.648), type of pharmacy field (p=0.968), and years in the profession (p=0.331), there were no significant differences in terms of knowledge about COVID-19 medication and vaccines. The p-values for all these groups were higher than 0.05, which means acceptance in the null hypothesis. This shows that even if there were some significant differences in scores between men and women, or between different types of pharmacists or those with different experience levels, they are not statistically significant. This is interpreted as everyone is still learning about these topics, and no single factor stands out as having more knowledge than others.

In the study done with hospital pharmacists in Lebanon in regard to their knowledge, attitude and practice towards COVID-19 pandemic, the study showed results that the demographic profile has no significant effect on the knowledge of the pharmacists (Zeenny et al., 2020). In the study done for hospital and community pharmacists in Ethiopia, survey results showed that the demographics of their respondents did not show significant effect on their knowledge (Dereje et al., 2021). Another study done to assess the knowledge of community pharmacists in Pakistan has shown that pharmacists regardless of the demographics somehow have the same amount of knowledge in regard to COVID-19 medication and vaccine (Muhammad, et al., 2020).

So far, there has only been one approved medication and one authorized vaccine to combat the disease COVID-19. Pharmacists are considered as the medication experts in the healthcare field, and it is interesting and somehow comforting to see the results that came up from this study. Majority of the respondents know the correct information about the basic information about the available medication and vaccine for COVID, except for one which was for the pharmaceutical company that produced and manufactured the product. The mean scores of the respondents that were divided among specific demographic profile has shown that pharmacists are still on the emerging spectrum when it comes to their knowledge about COVID-19's medication and vaccine, this is adequate for now as this disease has really taken the healthcare profession by storm. Pharmacists having emerging knowledge can only mean that they are trying their best to learn at the same time as new information is coming out.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Respondents are still learning about COVID-19 knowledge on vaccination and medication. Most of the sources of knowledge about COVID-19 vaccination and medication were taken from journals and social media by the respondents. Regardless of being a hospital or community pharmacist, they both still at a learning curve of knowing the Covid-19 vaccination and medication. In the same way, being male or female and having more years of pharmacy exposure still have at the learning curve of COVID-19 knowledge on vaccination and medication.

The hospital should create a plan on how to increase more knowledge-based about COVID-19 vaccination and medications that has a significant impact on the practice of pharmacy here in the Philippines. To increase awareness and knowledge, pharmacy professionals should attend virtual training sessions and/or conferences that will help them be more knowledge equipped about COVID-19 vaccination and medication. Private and government pharmacy associations can come up with monthly webinars and seminars that can help the pharmacists be updated with the recent changes and changes in the trend for COVID-19 medication and treatment. This will be very beneficial to the pharmacists to perform their jobs better and the sources of information would be reliable and trusted. Future researchers can do studies with a larger number of respondents and more extensive scope with all of the recent updates that have been available for the medications and vaccines used in the fight against COVID-19.

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